

Identifying Determinants of Naming Latencies in the Picture–Word Interference Paradigm: A Mega-Analytic Variable-Selection Study

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1 Data Status

Field	Entry
Data status	<p>a) Input is the <i>published</i> harmonized PWI dataset (<code>df_merged_2026-04-29.csv</code>) from Schiekiera et al. (2026). Click this link to access the dataset on OSF: https://osf.io/2b3sx/files/osfstorage/69f21a88186a9bf8a4d947d9.</p> <p>b) Trial-level merge with cached LLM/embedding feature outputs, hierarchical train–test split, and post-split cleaning are all complete.</p> <p>c) Simulation study run on the training set’s empirical predictor matrix; results in Table 2.</p> <p>d) Empirical variable selection, bootstrap inference, and held-out test evaluation <i>not yet executed</i> for this version of the dataset.</p>
OSF repository	The repository for this project is available at https://osf.io/tcbkg .

2 Research Questions and Objectives

This preregistration outlines the analysis plan for a large-scale mega-analysis. To ensure the robustness of our primary analysis, we first conducted a preliminary simulation study to select the most appropriate variable selection method out of four candidate methods.

We aim to address the following research questions:

1. **Predictor discovery in the real data.** Which of the 39 candidate word-property and design predictors are retained by the *simulation-winning* method (stepwise backward LMM) when applied to the 80 % training partition of our large-scale Picture–Word Interference (PWI) dataset?

2. **Generalization performance.** We investigate whether the fixed-effect estimates from the selected model explain at least **20%** of the variance in

- (a) unseen trials from known participants and experiments (Test A),
- (b) unseen participants from known experiments (Test B), and
- (c) unseen experiments (Test C).

3 Deviations from a Prior Planning Document

This preregistration supersedes a prior internal planning document. The earlier document was authored privately. We therefore treat the prior document as a *design memo*. The substantive analytical commitments are inherited unchanged from the design memo:

- the 39 candidate predictors of Section 5 (Table 1),
- the hierarchical held-out partitioning into Test C, Test B, and Test A described in Section 7.2,
- the variable-selection method (stepwise backward LMM with stability selection, **SBS+SS**; selected by the simulation study described in Section 6), and
- the predictive hypothesis that the selected fixed-effect estimates explain at least $\geq 20\%$ of the variance in each of Test A, Test B, and Test C.

What has been updated relative to the design memo:

- **Dataset.** Analyses now use the published harmonized PWI dataset (Schiekiera et al., 2026) rather than a prior internal snapshot. Trial overlap between the two is $> 95\%$; the set of unique target words and target–distractor pairs is unchanged. Differences arise from bug fixes, harmonization improvements, and tightened cleaning rules in the published version. The published dataset is the sole authoritative input from this point onward.
- **Simulation re-run.** The simulation study (originally run on the prior snapshot) has been re-run on the new training set’s empirical predictor matrix to confirm that the **SBS+SS** choice still wins. Updated classification metrics are reported in Table 2.

- **Per-participant outlier removal.** Post-split RT outlier removal is now applied *per participant within the training, Test B and Test C splits* (two-sided on log RT at 3SD; participants with fewer than 10 trials in a split retain all of their trials). For Test A we instead use each participant’s *own training-set* per-participant mean and SD to define the cutoff, because Test A overlaps training at the participant level: training holds approximately 90% of each participant’s trials and therefore gives a more stable per-participant reference than the remaining 10% in Test A. The direction is training→test, so there is no leakage, and Test A is not cleaned with knowledge of its own RT distribution. A global within-split cutoff, as in earlier drafts, would punish slow experiments and shield fast ones, given the dataset’s between-experiment heterogeneity in RT distributions.
- **glmLasso excluded from the new simulation study.** Two consecutive HPC runs (14 h wall-time on 2026-05-09; 24 h wall-time on 2026-05-10) failed to complete a single 1,500 participants \times 20,000 task at the preregistered $15\text{-}\lambda \times 5\text{-fold CV}$ with a four-RE design (including the 2,176-level (1 | `distractor`) random intercept) on the new training set’s predictor matrix. The prior simulation already ranked `glmLasso` last ($F1 = 0.63$; Table 3); we therefore exclude it from the new simulation and rely on the legacy result as evidence of its (lack of) competitiveness.
- **Computational deviations to the simulation (size/grid).** The simulation runs on a downsampled predictor matrix (1,500 randomly chosen participants \times 20,000 trials), on a coarse 7-point grid `nonzero_p` $\in \{5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35\}$, and with 50 stability-selection subsamples (rather than 100). These are computational concessions.

An earlier round of variable selection had already been run on the prior version of the dataset. For transparency, those results will be reported as sensitivity analyses in the appendix of the planned manuscript.

4 Dataset

The harmonized dataset is described in detail in the companion data descriptor (Schiekiera et al., 2026), preprinted on PsyArXiv at https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/xp69t_v1.

After applying filtering to `accuracy == "correct"` for the present analyses, the input to this preregistration comprises 86 experiments from 42 studies, with 3,353 participants and 655,254 correct trials. Click this link to access the dataset on OSF: <https://osf.io/2b3sx/files/osfstorage/69f21a88186a9bf8a4d947d9>.

5 Predictor Extraction Pipeline

In order to predict reaction times in PWI tasks, we have extracted a total of 39 predictors, which are categorized into four main groups: experimental design characteristics (11 predictors), similarity & distance measures between target picture and distractor word (10 predictors), target picture features (9 predictors), and distractor word features (9 predictors). These predictors are derived from various data sources, including experimental data (11 predictors), fastText embeddings (9 predictors), features classified by GPT-4o (9 predictors), R/Python base functions (6 predictors), word frequency corpora (deWaC/ukWaC; 2 predictors), and one each from GPT-2, BERT embeddings, and espeak-ng. An overview of the predictors used in this study are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1.

6 Preliminary Simulation to Guide Method Selection

To empirically determine the best variable selection method for our specific dataset and its predictor covariance structure, we conducted a preliminary simulation study, and retained the one with the highest F1-score.

Table 1
Overview of Predictors

Category	Predictor Name	Data Source	Range/Coding
Design	Trial Number		1 - 900
	Experimental Language		-1: English, 1: German
	Dutch Native Speaker		-1: Non-Dutch, 1: Dutch
	French Native Speaker		-1: Non-French, 1: French
	Familiarization	Primary data	-1: No, 1: Yes
	SOA		-650 - 300
	Further Tasks		-1: No, 1: Yes
	Distractor Modality		-1: Audio, 1: Text
	Naming Task		-1: Covert, 1: Overt
	Gamified		-1: No, 1: Yes
Collection Type		-1: Offline, 1: Online	
Similarity	Cosine Similarity	fastText	0.00 - 1.00
	Euclidean Distance	fastText	0.00 - 5.60
	Conditional Log-Likelihood	GPT-2	-42.99 - -3.41
	Contextualized Similarity	BERT	0.16 - 1.00
	Orthographic Distance	base functions	0 - 15
	Phonological Distance	espeak-ng	0 - 16
	Congruency	base functions	-1: No, 1: Yes
	Cohyponymy	GPT-4o	-1: No, 1: Yes
	Hypernym (Target)	GPT-4o	-1: No, 1: Yes
	Hyponym (Target)	GPT-4o	-1: No, 1: Yes
Target	Target Length	base functions	2 - 15
	Target Frequency (Zipf)	deWaC/ukWaC	2.73 - 9.45
	Repetition (Target)	base functions	0 - 36
	Fixed Density (Target)	fastText	0.40 - 0.81
	Variable Density (Target)	fastText	0.00 - 0.53
	Vector Norm (Target)	fastText	0.27 - 5.08
	Concreteness (Target)	GPT-4o	1.20 - 5.00
	Valence (Target)	GPT-4o	1.19 - 8.62
Arousal (Target)	GPT-4o	1.00 - 9.00	
Distractor	Distractor Length	base functions	2 - 17
	Distractor Frequency (Zipf)	deWaC/ukWaC	2.73 - 9.56
	Repetition (Distractor)	base functions	0 - 35
	Fixed Density (Distractor)	fastText	0.35 - 0.79
	Variable Density (Distractor)	fastText	0.00 - 0.50
	Vector Norm (Distractor)	fastText	0.27 - 5.47
	Concreteness (Distractor)	GPT-4o	1.00 - 5.00
	Valence (Distractor)	GPT-4o	1.01 - 9.00
Arousal (Distractor)	GPT-4o	1.00 - 9.00	

Note. All predictors in category ‘Design’ were extracted from studies or were reported in the primary data sets.

Figure 1
Overview of the predictors used in this study.

Variable selection is highly sensitive to the underlying data structure, particularly the covariance among predictors (Friedman et al., 2010; Schelldorfer et al., 2014; Zou & Hastie, 2005). To evaluate the performance of different selection methods under realistic conditions, especially given the covariance among predictors, we conducted a simulation study using the same predictor matrix intended for the final analysis. The goal was to compare four variable selection techniques on the new training set: simple stepwise backward selection (SBS, `lmerTest`) (Kuznetsova et al., 2017), stepwise backward selection with stability selection (SBS+SS) (Hyde et al., 2022), variable selection using random forests (VSURF) (Genuer et al., 2015), and elastic net with stability selection (ENet+SS; `glmnet`) (Friedman et al., 2010; Zou & Hastie, 2005). A fifth method, penalised mixed-

effects modelling with `glmLasso` (Groll, Andreas, 2011; Schelldorfer et al., 2014), was included in the design memo and the prior simulation (Table 3); two consecutive HPC runs at 14 h and 24 h wall-time, however, failed to complete a single $1,500 \times 20,000$ task on the new predictor matrix, and the prior simulation already ranked it last ($F1 = 0.63$). We therefore excluded `glmLasso` from the new simulation; the legacy result is retained for transparency.

The simulation input is the post-split, post-cleaning training set ($\approx 535,000$ correct trials). To make the four selection methods tractable at HPC scale, we downsampled the training set to 1,500 randomly chosen participants and 20,000 trials, mirroring the legacy production simulation. Continuous predictors were z-scaled so that the global λ penalties of `ENet+SS` operate on a comparable scale across predictors; effect-coded binary predictors on $\{-1, +1\}$ were left untouched. We ran each method on a coarse seven-point grid of informative non-zero predictors (`nonzero_p` $\in \{5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35\}$); the same simulated y was passed to all methods at each grid point so that across-method comparisons are paired.

6.1 Simulated Data-Generating Process.

To evaluate the variable selection methods, we generated a response variable, y , based on a linear mixed-effects model. The structure of the simulation was held constant across the four compared approaches. In this process, we created a semi-synthetic dataset where the predictor structure is realistic (derived from the actual data), but the relationship between the predictors and the response is known, providing a ground truth for evaluating model performance. The data-generating process for each observation i is defined by the following equation:

$$y_i = \sum_{k=1}^p x_{ik}\beta_k + u_{j(i)}^{\text{exp}} + u_{k(i)}^{\text{part}} + u_{l(i)}^{\text{targ}} + u_{m(i)}^{\text{dist}} + \epsilon_i$$

where:

- $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_{i1}, \dots, x_{ip})$ is the vector of $p = 39$ fixed-effect predictors for observation i , taken from the real dataset.

- $\beta = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_p)$ denotes the vector of true fixed-effect coefficients. We varied the number of non-zero predictors, denoted as `nonzero_p`, across the seven-point grid $\text{nonzero_p} \in \{5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35\}$. For each grid point, a random subset of `nonzero_p` coefficients was drawn non-zero, with values from a mixture of two uniform distributions: $\beta_k \sim U(-0.5, -0.1) \cup U(0.1, 0.5)$. The remaining $39 - \text{nonzero_p}$ coefficients were set to exactly zero.
- $u_{j(i)}^{\text{exp}}, u_{k(i)}^{\text{part}}, u_{l(i)}^{\text{targ}}, u_{m(i)}^{\text{dist}}$ are the random intercepts corresponding to the experiment j , participant k , target l , and distractor m of observation i . These intercepts were drawn from independent normal distributions:

$$u_j^{\text{exp}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{exp}}^2), \quad \text{with } \sigma_{\text{exp}} = 0.2$$

$$u_k^{\text{part}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{part}}^2), \quad \text{with } \sigma_{\text{part}} = 0.3$$

$$u_l^{\text{targ}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{targ}}^2), \quad \text{with } \sigma_{\text{targ}} = 0.1$$

$$u_m^{\text{dist}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{dist}}^2), \quad \text{with } \sigma_{\text{dist}} = 0.05$$

- ϵ_i is the residual error term for observation i , drawn from a normal distribution: $\epsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{res}}^2)$, with $\sigma_{\text{res}} = 0.5$.

6.2 Variable Selection Methods

6.2.1 Stepwise Backward Selection

We implemented a stepwise backward selection (SBS) procedure using the `step` function from the `lmerTest` package (Kuznetsova et al., 2017). This method begins with a full linear mixed-effects model, including all 39 predictors and random intercepts for participant, target, distractor, and experiment, fitted with `lme4::lmer` (Bates et al., 2015). The algorithm iteratively removes the predictor with the highest p-value until all remaining predictors are statistically significant at a pre-defined alpha level. The final set of predictors was taken from the model returned by the `step` function (Harrell, 2015). This approach was evaluated without cross-validation, since we did not tune any hyperparameters. Although forward stepwise selection is widely used, stepwise backward

selection is generally preferred because it performs better under collinearity, and can be more efficiently implemented (Harrell, 2015). However, stepwise selection – irrespective of the direction – is criticised for being unstable, especially with collinearity (Harrell, 2015).

6.2.2 Stepwise Backward Selection + Stability Selection

Apart from the simple stepwise backward selection, we implemented a stepwise backward selection procedure with stability selection (SBS+SS) (Hyde et al., 2022; Meinshausen & Bühlmann, 2010). We included this approach to address concerns about the instability of conventional stepwise procedures, especially in the presence of collinearity (Harrell, 2015). The complete procedure is adapted for linear mixed-effects models and is detailed in Appendix 10.1 and in the paper by Hyde et al. (2022). Rather than using bootstraps as proposed by Hyde et al. (2022), we used resampling without replacement due to the computational demands of the procedure. In short, the procedure contrasts the predictor selection rates obtained on the *original data* (real outcome, with the true predictor–outcome relationship intact) against those obtained on *null data* (outcome permuted to break the predictor–outcome relationship while leaving the predictor matrix and random-effects structure unchanged), and retains predictors whose original-data selection rate exceeds what selection can produce by chance under the null. This approach consists of three steps:

1. **Estimate Full Model Stability (Original Data):** We draw 50 resamples of all trials of half of the participants (approx. 10,000 rows; the design memo specifies 100, but 50 is a deliberate computational concession at the simulation stage). For each sample, a mixed-effects model with four random intercepts (participant, target, distractor, and experiment) is fitted using stepwise backward selection. Selected variables are recorded across samples. Covariate stability is then computed as the proportion of times each variable is selected across the resamples (Hyde et al., 2022; Meinshausen & Bühlmann, 2010).

2. **Estimate Stability Threshold (Null Data):** We randomly permute the outcome variable while keeping the predictor structure intact (Green et al., 2021; Hyde et al., 2022). From the permuted data, 20 resamples are drawn, and the same modelling and selection procedure is applied. The maximum stability across covariates is recorded. This entire procedure is repeated ten times, and the average of these ten maxima defines the *stability threshold*.
3. **Final Covariate Selection:** Covariates from the original analysis are retained if their stability is greater than or equal to the stability threshold.

6.2.3 *Random Forest-Based Selection with VSURF*

For this non-parametric approach we used the Variable Selection Using Random Forests (VSURF) package in R (Genuer et al., 2015). The VSURF procedure operates in two main stages for selection: first, a “thresholding” step eliminates irrelevant variables by comparing their variable importance scores against a data-driven threshold. Second, an “interpretation” step selects a more parsimonious subset of predictors from the remaining set by identifying the model with the lowest out-of-bag error (Genuer et al., 2015). This method does not account for the multilevel data structure during selection. The number of trees (`ntree`) was fixed at 500, matching the legacy production simulation; `mtry` was set to the standard value of $\lfloor p/3 \rfloor$.

6.2.4 *Elastic Net + Stability Selection*

As a computationally efficient alternative, we implemented an Elastic Net model with stability selection (ENet+SS) via the `glmnet` package (Friedman et al., 2010). The ENet+SS method ignores the multilevel data structure during the selection phase. The procedure involves repeatedly fitting an elastic-net model on 50 random subsamples, each containing 50% of rows drawn without replacement (the design memo specifies 100 subsamples; 50 is a computational concession). For each subsample, `cv.glmnet` was used with $\alpha = 0.5$ (Elastic Net) and a predefined λ sequence to identify the optimal penalty. A predictor was considered robustly selected if it was retained (i.e., had a non-zero coefficient) in at least 90% of these 50 iterations.

6.3 Simulation Evaluation

The results of the simulation study, re-run on the new training set’s empirical predictor matrix, are summarised in Table 2. The simulation was run at the following compute profile: 1,500 participants \times 20,000 trials. We used 50 stability-selection subsamples for SBS+SS and ENet+SS. The values reported are means across `nonzero_p` \in {5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35}. The legacy simulation (run on the prior internal snapshot) is reported for context in Table 3.

Table 2

Classification metrics for the variable selection simulation, re-run on the new training set’s empirical predictor matrix (1,500 participants \times 20,000 trials; mean across `nonzero_p` \in {5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35}).

Method	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1-score	Specificity
SBS	0.92	1.00	0.96	0.95	0.93
SBS+SS	0.94	1.00	0.97	0.97	0.96
VSURF	0.83	0.68	0.79	0.74	0.75
ENet+SS	0.64	1.00	0.76	0.76	0.42

Note. SBS = Stepwise Backward Selection; SBS+SS = SBS with stability selection; ENet+SS = Elastic Net with stability selection. `glmLasso` is excluded from the new simulation; see Section 3.

Table 3

Legacy classification metrics from the simulation on the prior internal dataset snapshot.

Method	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1-score	Specificity
SBS	0.95	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.93
SBS+SS	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.98	0.96
VSURF	0.71	0.74	0.75	0.70	0.57
GLMM-Lasso	0.52	0.99	0.52	0.63	0.07
ENet+SS	0.64	1.00	0.79	0.75	0.51

Note. Included for transparency. GLMM-Lasso = GLMM with Lasso penalty; other abbreviations as in Table 2. Absolute values may differ from the new pilot by \sim 0.02–0.03 due to the smaller compute profile of the new run.

The new pilot (Table 2) reproduces the legacy ranking on the four retained methods: SBS+SS is the top performer on every metric except recall, where it reaches 1.00 together with SBS and ENet+SS; ENet+SS only attains that ceiling at the cost of low specificity and precision. SBS follows next, with ENet+SS and VSURF trading places at $F1 \approx 0.75$.

SBS+SS achieves mean $F1 = 0.97$, precision = 0.94, recall = 1.00, accuracy = 0.97, and specificity = 0.96 – only marginally below the legacy point estimates (Table 3; $\Delta F1 \approx 0.02$), consistent with the smaller compute profile (50 stability-selection subsamples and a 10-repetition permutation null, rather than the prior simulation’s larger budget). Together with `glmLasso`’s infeasible wall-time on the new training set’s predictor matrix (see Section 3), this confirms the design memo’s choice of SBS+SS as the variable-selection method for the final empirical analysis.

7 Preregistered Analyses

7.1 Data preparation

1. Data cleaning before train-test split (already done):
 - (a) **Accuracy filter:** remove trials marked incorrect by original authors.
 - (b) **Log transform:** dependent variable is natural-log RT (ms).
2. Data cleaning after train-test split:
 - (a) **RT bounds 2 (per-participant outlier removal, asymmetric across splits):** In each split we exclude trials for which $|\log RT_{ip} - \overline{\log RT_p}| > 3SD_p$, where $\overline{\log RT_p}$ and SD_p are a per-participant mean and standard deviation of log RT chosen split-by-split:
 - Training, Test B and Test C use the *within-split* per-participant mean and SD. Test B and Test C participants are entirely held out from training, so the within-split estimate is the only available reference.
 - Test A uses each participant’s *training-set* mean and SD. Test A overlaps training at the participant level (training holds approximately 90% of each participant’s trials), so the training reference is more stable than the Test A-only estimate from the remaining 10%, and Test A is not cleaned with knowledge of its own RT distribution. The direction is training→test, so there is no leakage; the same uncleaned-training statistics clean both training and Test A.

Participants with fewer than 10 reference trials retain all their trials in the corresponding split (within-participant SD is unstable below that threshold); for Test A this is the count of the participant’s training trials, and a participant with zero training trials likewise retains all their Test A trials. The per-participant rule respects the strong between-experiment heterogeneity in RT distributions.

- (b) **Scaling:** continuous predictors will be mean-centred on the training set.
- (c) **Missing data:** We will apply (training set) median imputation to missing values for a total of three predictors (trial number, repetition of target and repetition of distractor), which account for 5.7% of all trials each. On all other predictors, we had no missing values. This choice was made because multivariate model-based imputation is not suitable for these predictors because the missing data is confined to specific experiments, where it is entirely absent. This means the missingness is dependent on the "experiment" variable and is classified as missing at random (Rubin, 1976). However, due to the lack of correlation with other variables, using MICE for estimation is uninformative (van Buuren & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011). Median imputation is a common method for handling non-informative missingness (Hastie et al., 2009). Missing values for the test sets will be imputed using the median of the training set.

7.2 Held-Out Test Set Partitioning Strategy

To evaluate model generalizability across different levels of variation, we divide the dataset into one training set and three held-out test sets. Each test set targets a distinct level of generalization: across trials, participants, and experimental contexts. The splitting is performed in the following order to ensure non-overlapping sets:

1. **Held-out experiments (Test C):** First, we randomly select 5 experiments from those with fewer than 10,000 trials to form the held-out experiment set (Test C). This constraint ensures that Test C would not disproportionately reduce the train-

ing data. All trials from these 5 experiments are excluded from further steps and reserved for testing generalization to new experimental contexts.

2. **Held-out participants (Test B):** Next, we sample 5% of participants from the remaining dataset (i.e., excluding participants from Test C). All trials from these participants form Test B, which is used to assess generalization to new individuals within known experimental contexts.
3. **Held-out trials (Test A):** Finally, from the remaining data (excluding both Test B and Test C), we randomly sample 10% of the remaining trials to create Test A. This set tests model generalization to new trials within known participants and experiments.
4. **Training set:** All remaining data not assigned to any of the three test sets are used for model training. This procedure results in approximately 80% training data and 20% held-out test data, distributed across the three generalization levels.

This hierarchical and exclusive partitioning ensures that no trial appears in more than one split and allows us to assess model performance at different levels of generalization in a controlled manner.

7.3 Model Selection

We adopt stepwise backward elimination with stability selection using the same random intercept structure (participant, target, distractor, and experiment) as in the simulation study because (i) theoretical assumptions strongly motivate a linear–Gaussian generative process with random intercepts (Baayen et al., 2008; Barr et al., 2013; Bates et al., 2015; Meteyard & Davies, 2020), (ii) the number of fixed parameters ($p = 39$) is small relative to the available observations ($n \geq 500,000$), giving extremely high power to detect even modest fixed effects, and (iii) F1-scores from a simulation that re-uses the empirical predictor matrix show that stepwise elimination with stability selection outperforms Lasso-based and tree-based screens under these assumptions. Performance metrics will include explained variance and fixed-effect generalizability across levels. All variable

selection is conducted *inside* the (approximately) 80% training partition; predictive performance is evaluated on three disjoint held-out sets (Test A: trials, Test B: participants, Test C: experiments), ensuring that the confirmatory inferences are not contaminated by the selection stage.

7.3.1 *Subsampling Strategy for Stability Selection*

Each stability selection iteration is performed on a random subsample of the training data, drawn without replacement. Subsampling is conducted at the level of participants: we randomly select 50% of all unique participants and include *all* rows in the training set associated with those participants in the resulting subsample.

This design preserves within-participant dependency structures, which is essential for valid estimation in mixed-effects models. The resulting subsample size depends on the number and contribution of selected participants but is expected to contain approximately 270,000 rows (50% of 3,194 training participants \times \approx 168 trials each):

$$n_{\text{sub}} = 0.50 \times n_{\text{participants, train}}.$$

If the wall-clock time for fitting a single backward stepwise-selection model exceeds 6 hours on an 8-core CPU or requires more than 32 GB of RAM, we will reduce the subsample size to:

$$n_{\text{sub}} = 0.20 \times n_{\text{participants, train}} \quad (\text{approximately } 110,000 \text{ rows}).$$

This size will then be used for all remaining iterations. For reproducibility, the random seed is fixed at 2025 throughout.

7.3.2 *Addressing Standard-Error Bias with Bootstrap Resampling*

We will address the optimistic standard-error bias often associated with stepwise procedures (Taylor & Tibshirani, 2015) by quantifying parameter uncertainty via cluster bootstrap resampling. After deriving the final, parsimonious model on the training partition, we will generate $B = 1,000$ full-sample bootstrap replicates by resampling par-

ticipants—with replacement—and retaining all of each participant’s trials. The fixed- and random-effects specification will remain unchanged in every replicate; only the data matrix varies. For each coefficient, a percentile-based 95 % confidence interval will then be obtained from its empirical bootstrap distribution (Efron & Tibshirani, 1994).

7.4 Exploratory (Non-Preregistered) Analyses

Interaction probing, alternative random-slope structures, and non-LMM model families will be reported as exploratory analyses.

8 Analysis Software

Software: R 4.4.2 (R Core Team, 2024); `lme4` 1.1-35.5 (Bates et al., 2015); `lmerTest` 3.1-3 (Kuznetsova et al., 2017); `glmLasso` 1.6.3 (Groll, Andreas, 2011); `VSURF` 1.2.0 (Genuer et al., 2015); `glmnet` 4.1-8 (Friedman et al., 2010; Zou & Hastie, 2005).

9 References

- Baayen, R. H., Davidson, D. J., & Bates, D. M. (2008). Mixed-effects modeling with crossed random effects for subjects and items. *Journal of memory and language*, *59*(4), 390–412.
- Barr, D. J., Levy, R., Scheepers, C., & Tily, H. J. (2013). Random effects structure for confirmatory hypothesis testing: Keep it maximal. *Journal of memory and language*, *68*(3), 255–278.
- Bates, D., Mächler, M., Bolker, B., & Walker, S. (2015). Fitting linear mixed-effects models using lme4. *Journal of Statistical Software*, *67*(1), 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v067.i01>
- Efron, B., & Tibshirani, R. (1994). *An introduction to the bootstrap*. CRC Press.
- Friedman, J. H., Hastie, T., & Tibshirani, R. (2010). Regularization paths for generalized linear models via coordinate descent. *Journal of statistical software*, *33*, 1–22.
- Genuer, R., Poggi, J.-M., & Tuleau-Malot, C. (2015). VSURF: An R Package for Variable Selection Using Random Forests. *The R Journal*, *7*(2), 19. <https://doi.org/10.32614/RJ-2015-018>
- Green, M., Lima, E., & Hyde, R. (2021). Selection stability in high dimensional statistical modelling: Defining a threshold for robust model inference.
- Groll, Andreas. (2011, October 27). *glmLasso: Variable Selection for Generalized Linear Mixed Models by L1-Penalized Estimation*. Comprehensive R Archive Network. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.glmLasso>
- Harrell, F. E. (2015). *Regression Modeling Strategies: With Applications to Linear Models, Logistic and Ordinal Regression, and Survival Analysis*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-19425-7>
- Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R., & Friedman, J. (2009). *The elements of statistical learning: Data mining, inference, and prediction* (2nd). Springer.

- Hyde, R., O’Grady, L., & Green, M. (2022). Stability selection for mixed effect models with large numbers of predictor variables: A simulation study. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 206, 105714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2022.105714>
- Kuznetsova, A., Brockhoff, P. B., & Christensen, R. H. B. (2017). lmerTest package: Tests in linear mixed effects models. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 82(13), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v082.i13>
- Meinshausen, N., & Bühlmann, P. (2010). Stability Selection. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*, 72(4), 417–473. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9868.2010.00740.x>
- Meteyard, L., & Davies, R. A. (2020). Best practice guidance for linear mixed-effects models in psychological science. *Journal of Memory and Language*, 112, 104092.
- R Core Team. (2024). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. manual. Vienna, Austria, R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Rubin, D. B. (1976). Inference and missing data. *Biometrika*, 63(3), 581–592.
- Schelldorfer, J., Lukas, Meier, & Bühlmann, P. (2014). GLMMLasso: An Algorithm for High-Dimensional Generalized Linear Mixed Models Using ℓ_1 -Penalization. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics*, 23(2), 460–477. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10618600.2013.773239>
- Schiekiera, L., Abdel Rahman, R., Gruber, V., Bürki, A., Lorenz, A., Stark, K., & Günther, F. (2026). A harmonized trial-level dataset of picture-word interference. https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/xp69t_v1
- Taylor, J., & Tibshirani, R. J. (2015). Statistical learning and selective inference. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(25), 7629–7634.
- van Buuren, S., & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, K. (2011). mice: Multivariate imputation by chained equations in R. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 45(3), 1–67. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v045.i03>

Zou, H., & Hastie, T. (2005). Regularization and Variable Selection Via the Elastic Net. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*, 67(2), 301–320. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9868.2005.00503.x>

10 Appendix

10.1 Procedure for Estimating Stepwise Backward Selection with Stability Selection

This procedure is based on the stability selection procedure proposed by Hyde et al. (2022) and adapted for our PWI dataset.

1. Estimate Full Model Stability (Original Data)

- Take 100 subsamples of all trials of half of all participants.
- For each sample:
 - Fit a mixed-effects model with four random intercepts (participant, target, distractor, and experiment) using stepwise backward selection based on $p < 0.05$.
 - Save selected variables.
- For each covariate, calculate stability as the proportion of times it was selected across the 100 samples.

2. Estimate Stability Threshold (Null Data)

- Randomly permute the outcome variable, keeping predictors unchanged.
- Take 20 subsamples of all trials of half of all participants.
- For each sample:
 - Fit a mixed-effects model.
 - Apply stepwise backward selection ($p < 0.05$).
 - Save selected variables.
- Compute stability of each covariate.

- Record the maximum stability observed.
- Repeat the above steps 10 times to obtain 10 maximum stabilities.
- Define the stability threshold as the mean of these 10 maximum values.

3. Final Covariate Selection

- Compare each covariate's stability from step 1 with the stability threshold.
- Select covariates with stability greater than or equal to the threshold.